

HumanTech News | January 2025
The Final Stretch

Dear community,

We are officially in the final stretch of HumanTech! ✨

Since we embarked on this journey in 2022, we have been driven by collaboration, innovation, scientific excellence, and a shared mission to improve the construction industry — and we are committed to making this next chapter as impactful as ever.

Let's take a moment to reflect on our recent milestones and look ahead to the exciting progress still to come:

Pilots

In our efforts to explore how innovative technologies can address specific challenges in construction, we have made significant **advancements in our [five pilot projects](#)**, where we are deploying our technical approach. We have gathered across Europe to test and validate them in collaborative, hands-on demo sessions under real-world conditions and collected user feedback to refine our solutions. To share our achievements, we have launched the “HumanTech Pilots” campaign, featuring videos and articles that showcase our pilots in action and explain the benefits they bring to the construction industry and its professionals.

Training Resources

Our partners at the Technological University of the Shannon (TUS) Sustainable Development Research Institute, in collaboration with the rest of the HumanTech Team, have developed **10 Micro Learning Units (MLUs)** to bring advanced construction technology into the classroom. Each MLU is designed to make learning accessible, impactful, and engaging, inspiring the next generation of construction professionals.

Research & Publications

This period has seen great advancements in our [research and publications](#). We have shared our findings on robotics, artificial intelligence, and digital construction through a total of 15 **cutting-edge publications**.

Meetings & Events

We have continued participating in events to share our findings and results while connecting with the construction innovation community. These include [SpliTech](#) in Croatia, [Sustainable Places](#) in Luxembourg, and the webinar “[Empowering Social Inclusion in Construction](#): Leveraging Technology for a Diverse Workforce.” Additionally, our partners at TUS hosted our [General Assembly Meeting](#) in Ireland in September, where we discussed our latest developments and coordinated our next steps. Next up, ACCIONA will host our last General Assembly in Madrid.

Deliverables & Open Source Tools

Our latest [15 public deliverables](#) (detailed reports from our work) and [7 open-source tools](#) (including source code repositories and datasets related to many of our scientific publications) are now available on our website. These resources are designed to drive innovation and efficiency in the construction industry.

Tech4EUconstruction Cluster

Collaboration among the eight EU-funded projects in our [Tech4EUconstruction cluster](#) continues through **joint campaigns and activities**. Recently, we launched a [social media campaign](#) to promote our scientific publications on digital and circular building. Our next event will be at Hannover Messe, a key international platform for industrial transformation, in March 2025.

As next steps, we will organise pilot demonstrations and use case tests in Madrid and Switzerland to showcase real-world applications of our innovations and further advance our technologies, exploitation plans and stakeholder engagement.

Thank you for being part of this incredible adventure. Together, we are shaping the future of construction technology.

Stay tuned for updates on our results.

[Discover our latest developments](#)

Don't miss out! Follow us on our social channels and [subscribe to this newsletter](#) to stay updated.

Now, let's dive into our pilot projects, training resources, scientific publications, and construction innovation updates. Enjoy!

HumanTech Pilots

We are working hard to implement our [innovative technologies](#) through five pilot projects that target critical challenges in the construction industry — focusing on improving safety, resource efficiency, and precision and making the sector more appealing to a new generation of highly skilled and diverse workers.

In recent months, we have worked together to conduct demonstration sessions and assess the performance of these pilots. These are the results from our first sessions:

[Robotic application of mastic in concrete expansion joints](#)

In October 2024, colleagues from various partner organisations gathered at ACCIONA Construction's R&D centre in Madrid to demonstrate our robotic system for mastic application.

[Watch this video](#) to hear from **Anurag Bansal** and **Irati Rasines** as they showcase this groundbreaking technology and discover **user feedback**, highlighting how it enhances worker safety, reduces workplace injuries, and boosts productivity.

[Read insights from our experts](#) at ACCIONA, TECNALIA, SINTEF, and BAuA involved in developing this innovative solution.

[BIMxD-based autonomous robotic task planning](#)

In December 2024, we gathered in Germany at RPTU (Rhineland-Palatinate University of Technology) Kaiserslautern's demo centre to do the final

implementation and demonstration of our pilot focused on BIMxD-based autonomous robotic task planning.

Jason Rambach, HumanTech’s coordinator, said, “**This pilot aims to demonstrate the potential of fully digitalised construction sites in enabling robotic automation.** This pilot is a **key example of successful partner collaboration in HumanTech**, as it integrates components developed by different partners such as **RPTU** (scan-to-BIM and autonomous navigation), **CATENDA** (BIMxD platform), **STAM** (ontology for robotic demolition task), **SINTEF** (robotic end-effector), **BAUBOT** (robotic platform), **RICOH** (surround-view streaming with spherical camera), and **KAJIMA** (end-user).”

[Read the contributions](#) from the team involved in developing this innovation.

Stay tuned for updates on upcoming pilots, including autonomous bricklaying, exoskeletons, and scan-to-BIM processes for buildings and bridges!

HumanTech Training

#HumanTechTraining

We have created **10 Micro Learning Units (MLUs)** to teach cutting-edge skills related to our innovations in Higher Education, Vocational Education and Training (VET), and Continuing Professional Development (CPD). Each module is designed to be short (1 to 2.5 hours) and aims to be accessible and insightful for both trainers and students.

The materials focus on shaping the future of construction, covering topics such as:

- Digitalisation
- Worker safety
- Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence
- Smart, unobtrusive workers' protection and support equipment
- A new breed of Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs)
- Green technology and sustainability

[Explore these resources](#), and watch our colleague Martin Breen's video introducing them.

[Explore our training tools](#)

Interested in piloting these MLUs with your students? [Contact us!](#)

*Please note that this is a preliminary version of these resources and is subject to improvements.

At HumanTech, we are advancing knowledge through cutting-edge research. Explore our latest research papers and articles to stay updated on our developments.

- [Robots Adapting to the Environment: A Review on the Fusion of Dynamic Movement Primitives and Artificial Potential Fields](#)
- [HiPose: Hierarchical Binary Surface Encoding and Correspondence Pruning for RGB-D 6DoF Object Pose Estimation](#)
- [SG-PGM: Partial Graph Matching Network with Semantic Geometric Fusion for 3D Scene Graph Alignment and Its Downstream Tasks](#)
- [IFC Properties Validation Using Deep Graph Neural Network](#)
- [Federating cross-domain BIM-based knowledge graph](#)
- [Task Automation in Construction Sites: Robot Learning from Teleoperated Demonstrations](#)
- [How Many Robots Is Too Many? Findings About Single-Human Multiple-Robot Systems](#)

Discussion Forum Series

ADOPTING CIRCULAR INNOVATION TOOLS IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

STRATEGIES, SUCCESS STORIES
AND ENGAGING STAKEHOLDERS

REGISTER NOW

JANUARY 28, 2025

11:00 am - 12:00 pm CET

REINCARNATE

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- **WEBINAR | January 28: “Adopting Circular Innovation Tools in Construction.”** Join Reincarnate’s online event, led by its partner, Erasmus University Rotterdam, to explore practical strategies, success stories, and tools to help reduce waste, improve resource efficiency, and engage stakeholders across the construction sector. [Register here.](#)
- Our sister project BEEYONDERS is conducting its [first tests](#) with **autonomous road inspection vehicles** and **drone technologies**. Through their **road maintenance use case**, they aim to demonstrate how aerial drones, digital twins, and ground robots can assist in road maintenance decisions using sensors and advanced perception techniques.
- **Call for Abstracts | The 22nd European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production (ERSCP 2025)** conference will take place in Prague from September 15 to 18, 2025. Jan Valentin, the project coordinator of RECONMATIC and a member of its Steering Committee, invites researchers, scholars, and practitioners to submit proposals for oral presentations, thematic sessions, or poster presentations on the conference's key topics. [More information.](#)

To finish, one last recommendation

[The AEC Business Podcast](#)

explores the intersection of innovation, technology, and trends shaping the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industries, featuring insights from industry leaders and experts worldwide.

Thanks for reading,
The HumanTech Team

[Get in touch](#)

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